

Electrochemical Properties of Synthetic Fulvic Acids

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Synthetic fulvic acids have been prepared from each of catechol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, vanillin, glucose and gallic acid with and without glycine as the source of nitrogen by air oxidation in 0.5N sodium hydroxide solution at 32° in presence of clay, silt and sand fractions of soil as catalysts. They have been subjected to conductometric and potentiometric titrations which reveal their weak acid character and polyelectrolytic nature. The features of the titration curves, particularly the conductometric ones, are compared with those of the monomers, from which the nature of the functional groups has been suggested. The similarity of the behaviour of synthetic fulvic acids with their natural counterparts has been pointed out.

The amorphous heterogeneous dark brown or black organic material of soil is collectively termed humus. Researches have been carried out on humus for a period of more than one and a half century and a vast literature has accumulated¹. According to O'den², soil humus can be fractionated into four main parts. A prolonged extraction of soil or compost with alkali or ammonium hydroxide leaves an insoluble residue variously known as humus coal, humin or ulmin. Addition of mineral acid to the extract produces a precipitate. The humic material remaining in solution is the fulvic acid fraction. This corresponds to the crenic and apocrenic acids of Berzelius. The alcohol soluble fraction of the precipitate is known as hymatomelanic acid.

The electrochemical properties of both soil and synthetic humic acids have been studied by various workers^{3,4}. Freytag⁵ has studied the course of humification of glucose by 80% sulphuric acid and suggests that it occurs in the sequence; fulvic, hymatomelanic, humic acid, indicating a series type of relation and fulvic acid as the precursor of humic acid. If that is so then the electrochemical and other properties of fulvic acid are likely to be similar to those of humic acid. A comparative study is, therefore, called for. The work presented here aims at obtaining information on the conductometric and potentiometric behaviours of the synthetic fulvic acid. Uptil now synthetic humus has been prepared by oxidation and condensation of polyphenolic compounds in the solution phase⁴. Natural humus is assumed to be formed by similar reactions which may be catalytically influenced by the substrate present mainly in the form of clay, silt and sand fractions of the soil.

1. M. Kononova, *Soil Organic Matter*, Pergamon Press (1961).
2. S. O'den, *Kolloid Chem. Beihefte*, 1919, **II**, 75.
3. B. K. Seal (1963). Doctorate Thesis, University of Calcutta (Unpublished).
4. K. B. Roy (1965). Doctorate Thesis, University of Calcutta (Unpublished).
5. H. E. Freytag, *Soils and Fertiliser*, 1961.

EXPERIMENTAL

Humus was synthesised from each of catechol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, vanillin, glucose and gallic acid with or without glycine as the source of nitrogen by simple air oxidation in 0.5 *N* sodium hydroxide solution in presence of a catalyst surface. This was provided by either clay fraction or silt and sand fractions isolated from soil. For this purpose these fractions were isolated from samples of Darjeeling and Chinsura soils of West Bengal and freed from adhering organic matter by hydrogen peroxide treatment. After about one month of air oxidation humus was extracted with 0.5 *N* sodium carbonate solution, and the supernatant was separated from the residue (rejected) by decantation and filtration. In the filtrate humic acid was precipitated with hydrochloric acid at *pH* 2-3. The clear filtrate containing fulvic acid was freed from precipitate by centrifugation, and was treated with barium chloride followed by dilute sodium hydroxide solution till the *pH* was near about 7-8. At this *pH* fulvic acid was precipitated as barium fulvate. The precipitate was freed from electrolytes by cautious washing with distilled water and finally by mild dialysis. Fulvic acid was prepared fresh when desired by passing the barium fulvate suspension through a column of Amberlite IR-120 in its H-form.

Electrochemical Properties : In order to identify the functional groups and to determine their amounts and also to obtain some information about their relative orientation in a polyfunctional macromolecule, conductometric and potentiometric measurements have been used.

Conductometric Titrations : The conductometric titrations were carried out at 30° ± 0.1° with a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge using a 1000-cycle oscillator. The titrations were carried out continuously with sodium and barium hydroxides in a cell of comparatively low cell constant.

The conductometric titrations of the different preparations of fulvic acids with sodium hydroxide* are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fulvic acids prepared in presence of glycine when

Fig. 1.—Conductometric titrations with NaOH.

* For saving space only the sodium hydroxide titrations are shown in graphs. Those with barium hydroxide have a longer initial flat portion and the minima in the curves for fulvic acid preparations containing nitrogen are less well defined.

titrated with barium hydroxide* and sodium hydroxide (Fig. 2) show two distinct breaks indicating a dibasic behaviour and at the same time the general features of weak acids, similar to those obtained by Seal³ and later by Dutta and Mukherjee⁶ with soil fulvic acids.

Fig. 2.—Conductometric titrations of fulvic acids containing nitrogen with NaOH.

The preparations of fulvic acids in absence of glycine, i.e., nitrogen, show markedly different features in their titration curves (Fig. 1). Both with sodium and barium hydroxides two breaks are shown but they are less sharp and the initial drop is conspicuously absent*. Those with barium hydroxide have got a longer initial flat run* than those with sodium hydroxide. Since the fulvic acid preparations containing nitrogen are characterised by an initial lowering, whereas those without nitrogen do not do so, it is suggested that this may be due to the free $-\text{COOH}$ of the glycine residues. If this is correct then the m.e. of base corresponding to the minimum would likely be a measure of such $-\text{COOH}$ groups. Qualitatively, fulvic acid hydrolysates containing nitrogen do show the presence of glycine (by paper chromatography) in varying amounts but the verification of the above suggestion is possible only by means of quantitative analysis of glycine content.

• From Table I showing the b.e.c.'s corresponding to each inflexion it is evident that the b.e.c.'s of different fulvic acids without nitrogen (F) are relatively low and lie in the range of 300 to 550 m.e., whereas those with nitrogen [F(N)] have their b.e.c.'s in the range of 800 to 1440 m.e. The latter are of the same order as those observed with soil fulvic acids. The specific conductances of the fulvic acids at the second equivalence points with sodium hydroxide, i.e., of the sodium fulvate solution, vary from 10.53×10^{-5} to 21.68×10^{-5} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Table II) at 30° , whereas those of soil fulvic acids⁶ lie in the range of 36 to 65×10^{-5} $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 30° .

TABLE I

B.e.c. in m.e./100 gm. of fulvic acid

Fulvic acids	Without nitrogen			With nitrogen			
	NaOH	Ba(OH) ₂		NaOH		Ba(OH) ₂	
		1st inflex.	2nd inflex.	1st inflex.	2nd inflex.	1st inflex.	2nd inflex.
Catechol-F	445	445	790	500	1440	300	1240
Hydroquinone-F	550	515	685	260	990	220	1010
Resorcinol-F	340	315	595	700	1070	600	1080
Vanillin-F	—	—	—	460	1170	400	1140
Glucose-F	—	—	—	220	832	210	850
Gallic-F	—	—	—	220	880	280	860

* See foot note on page 435.

TABLE II

Fulvic Acids	Concentration	Specific	Specific
		Conductance	Conductance
		at = 0	at = 1
		mho cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁵	mho cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁵
Catechol-F(N)	0.011	14.2	15.5
Hydroquinone-F(N)	0.012	8.0	10.5
Resorcinol-F(N)	0.016	44.0	21.7
Vanillin-F(N)	0.018	21.2	19.5
Glucose-F(N)	0.016	9.1	11.9
Gallic-F(N)	0.020	11.8	13.5
Catechol-F	0.046	8.9	15.8
Hydroquinone-F	0.035	10.5	21.4
Resorcinol-F	0.026	7.9	14.6

In order to find out the similarity and dissimilarity of the original monomers with the corresponding fulvic acids the conductometric titrations of catechol, hydroquinone and gallic acid in aqueous solutions have been performed with sodium and barium hydroxides. The titration curves* are characterised in general by weak breaks compared to those of the corresponding fulvic acids. The single break in the titration of catechol and hydroquinone with baryta corresponds to the neutralisation of the two phenolic hydroxyl groups. The gallic acid titration curve shows a small initial lowering and a single break corresponding to

* In order to save space the graphs are omitted.

neutralisation of the $-\text{COOH}$ group and one of the phenolic hydroxyl groups. Hence, it may be concluded that, if any carboxyl group is present in the acidic substance, an initial drop in conductance will be noticed, whereas if it contains only phenolic hydroxyl then the conductance will increase from the beginning of titration. From a comparative study of the titration of fulvic acids and the corresponding monomers, it is possible to suggest that if the fulvic acids contain only phenolic hydroxyls but no carboxyl the conductivity titration curves would initially show a region of almost constant conductance which extends to the equivalence point in the case of barium hydroxide titration but only to a fraction of it in the case of sodium hydroxide titration.

From the Fig. 2 it will be seen that the conductometric titration curves of the fulvic acids containing nitrogen with sodium hydroxide are very similar in nature to that of gallic acids with sodium hydroxides. By analogy, the initial drops observed in the titration curves of fulvic acids containing nitrogen may be ascribed to the presence of a $-\text{COOH}$ group. It is probable that the latter are from glycine which is incorporated in fulvic acids during their preparation. The conductometric titration curves of the above fulvic acids with baryta* are also very similar in nature to that of gallic acid, except that in the case of the former, the conductance remains nearly constant after the initial lowering up to the first equivalence point, after which the conductance rises showing a break at the second equivalence point. Gallic acid shows the initial lowering but the constant conductance region† is not observed.

Potentiometric Titrations The potentiometric titrations were carried out with the help of a Cambridge pH meter. Fulvic acids containing nitrogen were titrated with sodium hydroxide in the absence and presence of sodium chloride. The titration curves are shown in Fig. 3. The end points were more accurately located by drawing the differential curves

Fig. 3.—Potentiometric titrations of fulvic acids containing nitrogen with NaOH.

(not shown) in the usual manner. The end points are not as distinct as those of the corresponding conductometric titration curves. Catechol and resorcinol fulvic acids show a single

* The graphs are not included.

† The graphs are omitted.

inflection, whereas hydroquinone, vanillin, glucose and gallic fulvic acids show two inflections. By comparison with the titration curve of gallic acid monomer* with sodium hydroxide, the first of the two inflections may be attributed to the $-\text{COOH}$ group and the other to the phenolic hydroxyl.

The titration curves with barium hydroxide* are very similar in nature to those with sodium hydroxide. Like the soil fulvic acids the total acidity values of the synthetic fulvic acids are nearly the same when measured by the potentiometric and conductometric methods (c.f. Tables I and III). The apparent pK_{av} values determined from the pH titration curves of synthetic fulvic acids with sodium hydroxide at 50% neutralisation are given in Table III. These values range from 3.55 to 5.75. The addition of salt (0.5 *N* sodium chloride) lowers the pK_{av} values by about 0.25 to 1.45 units (cf. Table III). The reported values of pK_{av} for soil fulvic acids⁶ range from 4.10 to 5.75 and are in good agreement with those reported here for the synthetic fulvic acids.

It is possible to calculate the pK_{int} values from the equation⁷,

$$\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} - \text{pH} = pK_{int} - 0.868\alpha\omega \bar{Z}$$

where $\alpha = r/n$, r is the average number of H^+ ions dissociated per molecule, calculated in the present case as the ratio of the m.e. of base added to the b.e.c., n is the average total number of such dissociable protons per molecule, \bar{Z} is the net average charge on the molecule and ω is the electrostatic interaction factor. Thus plotting $\left(\text{pH} - \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\right)$ against α the

pK_{int} may be found out as the intercept at $\alpha = 0$, since $\bar{Z} = 0$ when $\alpha = 0$. Figs. 4 and 5 show such plots in absence and presence of 0.5 *M* sodium chloride. The values of pK_{int} for the different fulvic acid preparations both in presence and absence of sodium chloride are given in Table III.

Fig. 4.—Determination of pK_{int} of fulvic acids.

* The graphs are omitted.

TABLE III

Fulvic acids	B.e.c. m.e. 100 gm with		pK_{av}		pK_{int}	
	NaOH	in	in	in	in	
	2nd (infl.)	absence of NaCl	0.5N NaCl	absence of NaCl	0.5N NaCl	
Catechol-F(N)	1490	4.65	4.40	4.65	4.40	
Hydroquinone-F(N)	970	5.50	5.10	4.25	4.00	
Resorcinol-F(N)	1020	3.55	3.30	3.70	—	
Vanillin-F(N)	1010	4.85	4.10	4.70	4.10	
Glucose-F(N)	830	5.75	4.30	4.30	4.00	
Gallic-F(N)	880	5.65	4.60	4.70	4.05	

The values of pK_{int} for synthetic fulvic acids are close to those for side chain carboxyl⁷, namely 4.7. It is to be noted from the Table that addition of salt lowers the values of pK_{int} . In presence of salts, the polyelectrolyte molecules become coiled and compact and some of

Fig. 5.—Determination of pK_{int} of fulvic acids in 0.5N NaCl.

the phenolic groups remain shielded from neutralisation reaction. Moreover, in presence of electrolytes some phenolic -OH groups take part in an exchange process, viz., $-OH + Na = H^+ + -ONa$. The observed pH drop in 0.5N sodium chloride corroborates this point. This is equivalent to a lowering of pK_{int} for these phenolic groups. Both these factors in different degrees are probably responsible for the lowering of pK_{int} in presence of salt.

Thanks are due to Dr. S. Aditya, Reader, Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta, for allowing free use of laboratory facilities.